

LINK TO ACCESS THE SHINY APP: [https://lmkfbn-let0cia-
lopes0martins.shinyapps.io/PCJ_analysis/](https://lmkfbn-let0cia-
lopes0martins.shinyapps.io/PCJ_analysis/)